

D4.3

First Consolidated Action Plan of Awareness and Communication Activities

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Abbreviations

EuBioNet: European Bioeconomy Network

MML: Mobilisation and Mutual Learning

1. Introduction

Transition2BIO is a 24-month Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project aiming to promote the transition to a **more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle by means of the bioeconomy**, contributing to the implementation of the updated 2018 European Bioeconomy Strategy. The project will build upon the results of the most relevant communication and education EU-funded projects and initiatives and implement an integrated package of **communication, awareness-raising and educational activities**, while actively **engaging the wider public, Member States and Regions**. On the other hand, its work will contribute expanding the **European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet)**¹ and further support its activities, consolidated within an own workpackage (WP4).

Initiated by the BIOVOICES² project in March 2018, the European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet) is a proactive alliance of **projects and initiatives** dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication and support.

1.1 The EuBioNet action Plan of Awareness and Communication Activities, shared among EuBioNet projects

“The projects belonging to the European Bioeconomy Network will define a joint consolidated action plan of communication activities to initiate or reinforce the existing synergies, and maximise the opportunities to, and the impact of, promoting the bioeconomy”³.

Updated Bioeconomy Strategy (2018)

The definition of a joint consolidated action plan of communication activities goes beyond the definition of a shared time plan of activities, as well as beyond promoting collaboration among projects and initiatives or exchange of good practices.

The European Bioeconomy Network action Plan of Awareness and Communication Activities, is an integrated set of activities aiming at maximising the efforts, increase the knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, coordination of joint activities and events.

The extensive supporting activities promoted by the EuBioNet in the last three years it has become a full-fledged network to maximize the impact of the Updated Bioeconomy Strategy 2018 (pages 84, 85, 86) and widely recognized as relevant and effective to reach his objectives.

In the first years the EuBioNet was initiated and partially supported by the BIOVOICES project. Since January 2021 the Transition2BIO project is undertaking the animation and coordination of the EuBioNet. Transition2BIO will also experiment innovative formats and activities to strengthening the impact of the EuBioNet and the projects involved in the network.

¹ <https://eubionet.eu/>

² <https://www.biovoices.eu/>

³ [A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

In this context:

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the EuBioNet, why it was created, the objectives, the mission as stated in the Updated Bioeconomy Strategy 2018, the online platform and the achievements since its creation in 2018.

Chapter 3 describes how the EuBioNet will be strengthened under the Transition2BIO activities, by:

- Expanding the European Bioeconomy Network members (projects and initiatives)
- Animating the community of the European Bioeconomy Network
- Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activities among projects
- Promote the involvement of EuBioNet members in Transition2bio activities and events

Chapter 4 summarizes shortly the outcomes of the 2020 annual EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop and how these outcomes will inform the next activities of the EuBioNet in Transition2BIO.

Chapter 5 outlines the outcomes of the 2021 annual EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop organized by Transition2BIO in April 2021 and how these outcomes informs the next activities of the EuBioNet in Transition2BIO.

Chapter 6 describes the **EuBioNet 2.0**, namely the **vision and activities** that will be undertaken to increase the EuBioNet effectiveness and impact, following the suggestions emerged during the last two Mobilisation and mutual learning activities of the EuBioNet (in November 2020 and in April 2021).

Chapter 7 provides an overview the EuBioNet action Plan of Awareness and Communication Activities, describing the objectives and the activities planned by the EuBioNet.

Chapter 8 is about the conclusion and the **Annex 1** summarizes the most relevant achievements and collaborations that took place thanks to the facilitation of the EuBioNet.

2. The European Bioeconomy Network

Initiated by the BIOVOICES⁴ project in March 2018, the European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet) is a proactive alliance of **77⁵ projects and initiatives** dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication and support.

Figure 1 The EuBioNet partners and initiatives

The main goal of the European Bioeconomy Network is to **maximise the efforts, increasing the knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, coordination of joint activities and events.**

2.1 Rational of creating the European Bioeconomy Network

In 2017, in the context of the BIOWAYS project, a series of interviews have been conducted to CSA projects promoting the bioeconomy. From these interviews it was evident that **CSA projects were working in silos** and there was **very poor exchange of knowledge and good practices** among them. During the 2017 BBI JU Stakeholder Forum, Brussels - Belgium, speech “The value of Europe’s citizens – aligning economic and societal expectations and needs” the experts in the panel and the moderator Christian Patermann shared the **urgent need of facilitating the collaboration and mutual learning among CSA projects.**

Since early 2018, the European Commission shared the above-mentioned needs. The first discussion among projects, in March 2018, was promoted by BIOVOICES and hosted by DG RTD-Dir F, Bioeconomy. As main outcome of this Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop, BIOVOICES took up the challenge of connecting projects and **launched the EuBioNet two months later.**

⁴ <https://www.biovoices.eu/>

⁵ Number of partners updated at 26/04/2021

2.2 The European Bioeconomy Network objectives

The European Bioeconomy Network works in close collaboration with the European Commission to ensure that the activities are focused to the objectives identified in the Updated Bioeconomy Strategy 2018 so that they will be properly communicated, addressed and implemented.

The European Bioeconomy Network projects benefit from the mutual promotion of outcomes, new partnerships, joint event planning and knowledge sharing.

It is clear that each project and initiative member of the EuBioNet has its own agenda, objectives and activities, nevertheless, the EuBioNet have set the following shared objectives, that are promoted through the various projects' activities:

Promote collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promote active engagement, open dialogue, interaction and collaboration among partners • facilitate networking and collaboration between projects and stakeholders • design a joint and consolidated action plan for the bioeconomy communication, education and stakeholders' engagement
Increase bioeconomy awareness and communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support the transition towards a more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle. • increase the awareness of environmental, societal and economic benefits of Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy • raise awareness on the European Commission policies, funding and activities in the bioeconomy
Creation of the innovation ecosystem for the bioeconomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stimulate the debate, knowledge sharing and mutual learning to address bioeconomy related challenges and opportunity • promote stakeholders' engagement and networking activities at European, National and Regional level • facilitate the co-creation of actionable knowledge for the different stakeholders • identify and diffuse impact-oriented strategies to boost the sustainable circular bioeconomy in Europe • support the Member States and regions in developing awareness, communication and education activities on Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy

2.3 The European Commission recognizes the importance of the European Bioeconomy Network

In October 2018 EuBioNet, after being recognized in the Updated Bioeconomy Strategy⁶ as a key player for promoting and communicating bioeconomy, was invited to organize the bioeconomy corner, showcasing several Bio-Based products at the high-level conference launching the European Bioeconomy Strategy on 22 October 2018 in Brussels "**Sustainable and circular bioeconomy, the European way**"

⁶ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/edace3e3-e189-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1/>

Figure 2: Commissioner Carlos Moedas visiting the Bioeconomy Corner

During the conference “**Bioeconomy Scene 2019**” the EuBioNet was invited to organize the official satellite workshop “The role of communication and education in promoting circular and sustainable bioeconomy at local, regional and national level” and the BioART gallery to showcase Bio-based products in the conference’s lobby.

Figure 3: The BioART Gallery in the conference’s lobby

In the last three years EuBioNet representatives have been invited to **present the initiative in several high level conferences, workshops and events.**

2.4 EuBioNet online platform

The EuBioNet platform was specifically dedicated to support the collaboration among the EuBioNet community.

For this reason the design of the whole online platform has revolved around community activities from the start.

2.4.1 News and events

The first area, and the most active in terms of interaction from the community registered users, it's surely the 'News and events' area. Each user, after logging in the platform, has a dedicated page to upload the news or events providing a detailed description, date of the event, images and links to related documents.

As stated above, this area is the most active within the community and has up to this date 206 news and events uploaded.

In the meantime this area has been recognized by the whole bioeconomy community as a reference point to disseminate on future activities mainly in European countries and beyond. The engagement of the EuBioNet community allows a wide spread of the information, that increased the impact of any single event.

Figure 4: The news and events page

2.4.2 Call for collaboration

The area 'Call for collaboration' serves as match making tool for activities organized from the community members looking for interested partners. The idea is to launch a call for collaboration to

search for interested partners.

Unfortunately, the EuBioNet partners have uploaded only 11 requests, suggesting that this area needs to be better valorized or improved.

Figure 5: The call for collaboration page

2.4.3 Achievements

The 'Achievements' area provides an overview of all the activities organized and facilitated from 2018 to 2021 by the EuBioNet. The list is constantly updated with the new achievements.

Figure 6: The achievements page

2.4.4 Project and initiative partners

These are two separate section and lists all the projects that subscribe to the EuBioNet with the link to the project website and the email contacts. Up to this date, 70 projects are registered while the initiatives will be growing in the next months. This part of the website will be improved to make it more user friendly and to better describe the projects and initiatives. In addition thematic clustering and visualisation of what projects are still active should be integrated as well as summarizing conclusions should be stated.

Figure 7: The projects partners page

2.5 EuBioNet social media channels

The social media channels of EuBioNet - European Bioeconomy Network are Twitter and LinkedIn.

In May 2019 a LinkedIn group reserved for EuBioNet members was launched. It was decided to open a listed group instead of a public page to allow members to share both events relevant to the EuBioNet and “Call for collaboration” (describing the activity, the type of collaboration foresee and what expertise is being sought).

Since the main contact for the EuBioNet are usually the coordinator and the communication manager of projects, the LinkedIn group was also launched to extend the participation of the other partners of the projects, as well as external stakeholders interested in the EuBioNet (or EuBioNet members’) activities.

To date the LinkedIn group has 120 members.

LinkedIn	
Discoverability	Listed group
Members	120
Created	May 2019
Link	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8793586/

Table 1: LinkedIn group data

The Twitter page of the EuBioNet channel was created in October 2018. Events and news from all the partner projects and associations of the network are published on this page.

To date the EuBioNet Twitter page has 1.005 followers.

Twitter	
Followers	1.005
Tag	@EuBioNet1
Created	October 2018
Link	https://twitter.com/EuBioNet1

Table 2: LinkedIn group data II

From the images below some of the data related to the impressions are shown, with monthly reference, obtained from the Twitter channel. The data reaches more than 10,000 tweet impressions in a month.

Figure 8 Twitter monthly impressions

As a general rule, the responsible for the communication of EuBioNet does a cross-check of the news and events published on the site and. If it has not already been published by the project/initiative partners on the LinkedIn group or if EuBioNet has not been tagged on Twitter, the news and events are published on the EuBioNet channels.

2.6 The EuBioNet Achievements

Since its creation in 2018, the EuBioNet promotes and facilitates several activities among projects, including:

- organization of **Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activities among projects**
- the definition of a shared **Annual Action plan** for bioeconomy communication, education and Stakeholders' engagement
- **collaborations and organisation of joint activities** among projects
- **valorisation of outcomes, lessons learnt and exploitable assets** stemming from ongoing and concluded projects

2.6.1 Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activities among projects (partner's annual meetings)

Since its creation, the European Bioeconomy Network organises **at least one Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop each year**. This activity involves most of the projects and the objective is to stimulate the discussion around specific topics of common interest.

One of the objectives of this activity is the definition of a shared **Annual Action plan** for bioeconomy communication, education and stakeholders' engagement, as stated in the 2018 update of the European Bioeconomy Strategy.

The EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops are typically organized as part or as satellite events of European and international conferences, to reach higher impacts and ease the participation of the partners.

The next tables briefly summarize the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops organized in the past. The first activity organized by Transition2BIO is reported in Chapter 5.

"Facilitating collaboration among EU funded CSAs in bioeconomy"	
When	28 March 2018
Where	Brussels, Belgium Hosted by the European Commission, DG RTD-Dir F, Bioeconomy
Objective	The projects participating presented, shared and discussed the lessons learnt from their projects, identifying best and worst practices and expressed the willing to define a common action plan to align projects' activities.
Participants	27 projects, mainly Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs): BioLinX, ISAAC, BIOPOLIS, BIOWAYS, SuperBIO, ISABEL, BioHorizon, RoadToBio, DEMETER, BIOrescue, STAR4BBI, BioCannDo, BIOPEN, STAR-ProBio, SIM4NEXUS, BLOOM, BIOVoices, BIOSMART, BIOBRIDGES, T2gE - Transition to Green Economy, BioSTEP, CommBeBiz, EMBRACED, PLATFORM, OPEN-BIO, InnProBio, KBBPPS.

Impact	More than 35 participants, including project officers and policy officers
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This workshop highlighted the need to have a structured entity facilitating the collaboration among projects (but also networks and initiatives supporting bioeconomy). • This workshop Kicked-off of the European Bioeconomy Network.

Table 3: Overview of the 28 March 2018 MML

“The role of communication and education in promoting circular and sustainable bioeconomy at local, regional and national level”	
When	8 July 2019
Where/context	<p>Helsinki – Finland</p> <p>Satellite event of the High-level event organized by the EC “Bioeconomy Scene” July 2019</p>
Objective	<p>Bring together EU funded projects, European Platforms and Networks, Member states networks, together with quadruple helix stakeholders dealing with communication and awareness raising, to support the European Bioeconomy Strategy through communication activities.</p> <p>Promote the discussion and sharing of lessons learned and best communication practices, formats and channels; successful activities, multipliers to be involved; messages and arguments to be used (in terms of style, scope, terminology), etc.</p> <p>Facilitate the creation of synergies to maximise the opportunities and impact of bioeconomy communication at national and European Level.</p>

Participants	<p>European Commission, DG Research & Innovation The EU updated Bioeconomy Strategy, BBI JU, JRC Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy (KCB), European Economic and Social Committee, European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, European Network for Rural Development (ENRD), Urban Agenda, BIOEAST initiative.</p> <p>Projects: BioCannDo, LIFT, Biobridges, BIOWAYS, BioSTEP, BLOOM, CommBeBiz, DANDELION, DiReBio, DITOs, RoadtoBio, Pilots4U, MARINA, BE-Rural project, AlpBioEco, Green Growth Interreg Med</p>
Impact	73 participants
Outcomes	<p>Promote cross-projects analysis of effective communication formats.</p> <p>Supporting the European Bioeconomy Strategy through communication activities.</p>

Table 4: Overview of the 8 July 2019 MML

Mobilisation and Mutual Learning among CSAs projects supporting the Bioeconomy	
When	3 December 2019
Where/context	Brussels BBI JU Stakeholder Forum 2019 (project's day) co-organisation with the LIFT project of 11 parallel thematic sessions, involving CSAs projects.

Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight the good practices of past and ongoing Coordination and Support Actions (CSA) (FP7, H2020, BBI JU, Erasmus+ and Interreg), to valorise the projects' outcomes • Identify what are the existing gaps and challenges still to be addressed in the topical categories identified • Provide actionable recommendations for promoting an innovation ecosystem for Bio-based economy • Provide Suggestions for new topics to be addressed in Horizon Europe • Facilitate the networking, knowledge sharing and collaboration between the projects addressing similar topics
Participants (case studies)	<p>BIOWAYS, BioCannDo, BIOVOICES, BioSTEP, BIOWAYS, BioCannDo, BLOOM, UrBioFuture, InnProBio, ABBEE, InnProBio, STAR4BBI, STAR-ProBio, RoadToBio, BERST, BioStep, POWER4BIO, BE-RURAL, CELEBIO, BIOEASTsUP, BioSTEP, BLOOM, BIOVOICES, Biobridges, POWER4BIO, BE-RURAL, ProBio, CommBeBiz, BIO-TIC, BISO, Biomonitor, BIO-TIC, RoadToBio, BiOPEN, S2BIOM, STAR-ProBio, BioReg, ICT-BIOCHAIN, ENABLING, BioReg, ICT-BIOCHAIN, BiOPEN, POWER4BIO, BE-RURAL, RUBIZMO, BIOPEN, Pilots4U, ERIFORE, SmartPilots, SuperBio, BioBase4SME</p>
Impact	<p>38 projects presenting case studies, 280 participants</p>
Outcomes	<p>Mutual learning among projects grouped in 4 macro categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication and education • Policy framework • From research to market • Value chains and innovation ecosystem <p>11 Factsheets along the following 11 topical categories (published by LIFT project⁷):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising • Bioeconomy Education • Stakeholders engagement and co-creation • Standardisation, LCA, labelling and regulatory hurdles • Regional potential, bioeconomy strategies and action plans • Uptake of RTD results • Foresight, market studies and market roadmaps • Industrial roadmaps • Biomass availability, quality, supply and sustainability • New value chains and business models • Open innovation platforms and facilities

⁷ <https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/factsheets/>

Table 5: Overview of the 3 December 2019 MML

“Bioeconomy Communication and Stakeholders’ engagement in times of COVID-19”	
When	11 November 2020
Where/context	Online Towards the Global Bioeconomy Summit (16-20 Nov 2020)
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share experiences and Lessons Learnt on Bioeconomy Communication and Stakeholders’ engagement during COVID-19. • Discuss and share ideas and solutions to maximise the impact of project’s activities in the current times. • Provide inspirational ideas and good practices for the future EuBioNet partners’ activities. • Provide ideas and recommendations for the EuBioNet activities under Transition2BIO. How to strengthening the impact of the network?
Participants (case studies)	LIFT, BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BLOOM, BIOEASTsUP, BE-Rural, POWER4BIO, AlpBioEco, Allthings.bioPRO, BIOSWITCH, Transition2BIO.
Impact	11 projects presenting case studies, 85 participants

Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good practices on communication, education and stakeholder engagement in times of COVID (what worked, what should be improved) • Brainstorming and recommendations to increase the impact of the EuBioNet • Joint timeplan (November 2020 to June 2021) of Awareness and Communication Activities, shared among EuBioNet projects • Recommendations for the future of the EuBioNet under Transition2BIO.
Additional materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to the Agenda • Link to the event presentation • Link to the full video recording of the event

Table 6: Overview of the 11 November 2020 MML

Some outcomes of this workshop have been guiding the activities of the first EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop, as well as the new activities (the so called EuBioNet2.0), in Transition2BIO. Therefore, these outcomes are reported in Chapter 4.

2.6.2 Facilitating collaborations and organisation of joint activities

Thanks to the EuBioNet facilitation, more than **200 joint activities** and events took place. These collaborative activities will continue to be facilitated and promoted by the EuBioNet in 2021 and 2022 (under the Transition2Bio project). Examples of these activities are:

- Co-organisation of events and focus groups to discuss the key challenges to be addressed for bioeconomy,
- Organisation of awareness raising activities in large scale events (Maker Faire, Researchers' Night, Bioeconomy Village, Bioeconomy corner at the Sustainable and circular Bioeconomy, the European way and Bioeconomy Scene 2019),
- Involvement of EuBioNet members as experts/speakers in bioeconomy-related events (Workshops, Advisory boards, conferences, webinars),

- Increased impact of other project's outcomes (Promotion of events and activities organised by other members, dissemination of other members' project's results, facilitate connection and matchmaking of similar activities).

Annex 1 describes the most relevant achievements in terms of collaborations and organisation of joint activities and the projects involved, for years 2018 -2021.

3. Transition2BIO activities to strengthen the European Bioeconomy Network

This chapter explains how the European Bioeconomy Network will evolve, in 2021 and 2022, under the support of the Transition2BIO project, building on the work done since 2018 under BIOVOICES project.

The main objective is to maximise the collaboration among EU-funded bioeconomy projects and their collective impact. This will be achieved through the following activities:

- Expanding the European Bioeconomy Network membership involving new projects and initiatives (Paragraph 3.1)
- Animating the European Bioeconomy Network community, facilitating the collaboration among partners (Paragraph 3.2)
- Organising the Annual Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops of the European Bioeconomy Network (Paragraph 3.3)
- Supporting the definition of the joint action Plan of Awareness and Communication Activities, shared among EuBioNet projects (chapter 5)
- Implementing new formats and activities: The EuBioNet 2.0 (chapter 6)

3.1 Expanding the European Bioeconomy Network members (projects and initiatives)

To increase the impact of the EuBioNet activities in all member states and to address the missions listed for the EuBioNet in the update of the Bioeconomy Strategy, it is necessary to involve additional partners, in particular initiatives promoting the uptake of bioeconomy in Europe.

In order to reach that aim, the EuBioNet is implementing a series of activities informing and involving additional participants to the European Bioeconomy Network, namely:

- Participate to relevant events to promote the EuBioNet objectives and activities
- Map the new funded projects in different domains (H2020, Horizon Europe, BBI JU, other relevant partnerships, Erasmus +, Interreg, etc.)
- Contact directly relevant initiatives
- Promptly respond to spontaneous interest and requests by potential members
- Select the relevance of potential project and initiatives to keep the focus of the EuBioNet

This activity foresees also the engagement of new relevant partners such as BBI-JU, BIC, SCAR

Bioeconomy Strategic Working Group, JRC Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy, Committee of the Regions, European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, Bioeconomy Stakeholder Panel, Urban Agenda Partnership on Circular Economy, European Network for Rural Development, BIOEAST Initiative, European Economic and Social Committee, FAO, OECD, SUBMARINER network, etc. Some of these initiatives have already expressed their interest and discussions are in place for inviting them to be part of the network and to agree on future collaborations.

As an example, collaborations with JRC Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy and BIOEAST initiative are already taking place in form of speeches, organisation of joint training, support to member states and regions through info-training and future capacity building activities.

In May 2021, a **recruitment campaign will be launched** to involve additional partners. This will take place by:

- Sending individual invitations to become partners, highlighting the advantages of being part of the EuBioNet. This will use GDPR compliant databases (e.g. registered participants to events that showcased their interest)
- Supporting the recruitment activities with social media campaigns, supported by quotes from the actual partners and video-interviews to highlight the main advantages of being part of the EuBioNet
- Organizing individual/small groups meetings to discuss, not only the partnership, but also possible collaborations
- Contacting the new projects funded recently

The target declared in the Grant Agreement is to have at least 80 EuBioNet partners by the end of the project.

3.2 Animation of the European Bioeconomy Network

This activity aims at animating the collaboration among the members of the European Bioeconomy Network to consolidate and reinforce the existing synergies, maximise the opportunities and the impact of bioeconomy promotional activities.

In the first 2 years of its activity, the EuBioNet facilitated the creation of trusted relation and networking breaking down the silos between projects, promoted mutual learning and knowledge sharing, coordination of joint activities and events and enabled the definition of common activities among its members and beyond.

- More than 200 collaborations and joint activities took place thanks to the EuBioNet facilitation (Annex 1 lists the most relevant).
- 206 events have been promoted through the EuBioNet platform and shared on the EuBioNet social media pages (Twitter and LinkedIn).

Transition2BIO will keep alive this effective support, by facilitating collaboration, mutual learning, debate, joint projects, exploitation and valorisation of results, etc. (see details in Paragraph 2.2).

This activity takes place through a day-by-day activity of mobilisation and animation of partners, promoting engagement, suggesting joint activities and facilitating the networking and collaboration among partners.

The ideas co-created with the partners in the last two annual Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops (November 2020 and April 2021) are expected to facilitate the animation of the community and increase the impact of the project's activities and results. (see chapter 6).

A good example is the creation of the Thematic working groups. From mid May 2021, the first EuBioNet working group (in Bioeconomy Education) will be launched. The setup and launch of this first working group will provide some insights and lessons learnt for the set-up of the other Thematic working groups. (see paragraph 6.1)

In addition, the recruitment campaign that will take place from May, is expected to be an opportunity to share ideas with new actors and facilitate the connection with the other partners with them.

The target declared in the Grant Agreement is “to facilitate of at least 50 collaborations among EuBioNet partners in Transition2BIO”.

3.3 Organisation of the Annual Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops (MML) of the European Bioeconomy Network

In the context of Transition2BIO, two (2) MML workshops will be organized to bring the EuBioNet community together, to align their communication activities and define strategies to maximise the impact and reach all member States (including the less mature ones).

The first MML workshop has been organized in April 2021 (see outcomes in chapter 4).

The second annual MML workshop will be organized on M16.

Beyond the 2 MMLs foreseen, the consortium will exploit any relevant opportunity to facilitate the collaborative work of the project's members, especially in the context of high-level events and initiatives organized or supported by the EC.

The MML workshops will:

- Promote knowledge sharing, lessons learnt exchange and identification of solutions to address the challenges
- Promote networking, initiating or reinforcing existing collaborations and synergies
- Discuss and define a joint consolidated action plan of communication activities to maximise the opportunities and increase the impact for the promotion of bioeconomy.
- Make sure that the projects' joint communication action plan is fully aligned with the EC priorities, by involving EC representatives in the design of the workshops' contents and during the workshop activity.

During the second workshop, the Transition2BIO experiences in WP1 (Creation of awareness, communication, and education toolkits), WP2 (Awareness and public engagement activities) and

WP3 (Supporting Member States and Regions) will be shared, promoting the exploitation of the Transition2BIO Actionable Knowledge by other projects and initiatives having similar objectives.

The target declared in the Grant Agreement is to organize at least 2 Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshops.

3.1 Promoting the EuBioNet services

One of the main results of the EuBioNet is the possibility to identify and connect the most suitable projects and initiatives to be involved in joint activities and action plans.

As an example, the EuBioNet is promoting the support Member States and Regions in their awareness, communication, education, and stakeholder engagement activities to facilitate the implementation of strategies and action plans for the bioeconomy, through the joint activities of projects like Transition2BIO, BIOVOICES, BIOEASTup, Be-Rural, Power4BIO, AlpBioEco, etc.

One of the objectives for the next years is to strengthening this facilitator/connector role of the EuBioNet, through the creation of the Thematic Discussion Groups.

Another emerging idea stemming from the first MML is the creation of a collaboration marketplace, where needs and offers of services, but also partnerships, can be published.

Finally, to raise awareness about the EuBioNet services, the participation to conferences, events, and workshops, as in the previous years, will be encouraged.

4. Outcomes of the 2020 annual EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop

In the annual EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop that was organized in November 2020 by BIOVOICES, two sessions were dedicated to:

- Brainstorm and provide recommendations to increase the impact of the EuBioNet
- Define a shared time plan (November 2020 to June 2021) of Awareness and Communication Activities, involving the EuBioNet projects. This time plan was used to discuss possible collaborations among partners.
- Collect recommendations for the future of the EuBioNet under Transition2BIO

The workshop took place online and therefore MIRO boards have been used to stimulate the discussion. A brief overview of the event is provided in paragraph 2.6.1.

Figure 9 Discussion board “How can the EuBioNet contribute to increasing the impact of projects’ activities?”

The following points/suggestions emerged from the discussion “How can the EuBioNet contribute to increasing the impact of projects’ activities?”

Type of activity	Suggestions from participants
Promote collaboration, increase the knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize/Promote more the events like this • Team up of projects regarding topics • Support linking projects together and exploiting each other results • Organise regular short online meetings of the EuBioNet partners to specific topics to exchange our experiences. • Having more events like this with other topics and inviting other projects with common objectives • Do more cross-dissemination between EuBioNet and the projects • Interaction with other sectors (and funding sources, like Interreg) to learn from each other • knowledge exchange like today every 6 months
Expand EuBioNet membership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include the food sector too? (the oldest bioeconomy activity) • Extend more to initiatives (e.g. BBI JU, BIC, AKIS, Bioeconomy Strategic Working Group (BSW), European Circular Bioeconomy Fund (ECBF), JRC KCB, Europabio, ICLEI Circular, Euroconsumers, CoP Education, Bioladies, etc.)
EuBioNet website and social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event page is great! Keep it up • Create an internal platform to exchange ideas/talk...just like a social network • Use social media especially twitter to inform about EuBioNet initiatives • we should create opportunities to network online
Clustering projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choose specific topics within bioeconomy to merge collaborations of different projects • Promote EuBioNet Thematic groups: (examples: food system, packaging, waste, education.) Better link them to current EU policies
Stimulate the debate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise joint events addressing bioeconomy topics • Position paper integrating opinions from different projects • Include brand owners and consumers to the workshops like this as speakers
Coordination of joint activities and events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of shared time plan • Keep a joint list of planned projects’ events • You should organise a meeting with interested EuBioNet partners (every 3 months for instance), discussing about future events to co-organise

<p>Boost the innovation ecosystem for the bioeconomy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • connect the project with the overall goals of the region/country like regional development, EU integration (for candidate countries) • Capacity Building while Fostering B2B. C2C and Brokering
<p>EuBioNet future</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Turn EuBioNet into an association

Table 7: Suggestions emerged during the collaboration activity

Based on these insights and also taking into considerations additional suggestions provided in the various meetings that took place in the last months, the preliminary ideas for improvements have been structured in a conceptual map, that was shared in the EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop that took place in April 2021 (see chapter 5).

5. Outcomes of the 2021 annual EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop

This Chapter analyses the outcomes of the 2021 Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activity (the first in the context of Transition2BIO), that took place in April 2021 and describes how these outcomes will inform the next activities of the EuBioNet.

The annual Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activity of the EuBioNet was organized in collaboration with BIOVOICES, in the context of the BIOVOICES final event. This decision was made in order to bridge symbolically the two projects, by creating a strong sense of continuity among the activities.

The table below provides an overview of the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshop:

“Bioeconomy Communication and Stakeholders’ engagement in times of COVID-19”	
When	22 April 2021
Where/context	Online In collaboration with BIOVOICES final event
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attract additional projects and initiatives to the EuBioNet • Define a common vision/mission for the EuBioNet 2.0: the European Bioeconomy Network of the future. How to improve the activities and platform to increase the EuBioNet impact? • Share the planned activities of the projects to design the joint action plan • Collect Actionable Knowledge from projects to maximise their awareness, adoption and exploitation.

<p>Participants (projects)</p>	<p>BIOVOICES, Transition2Bio, Biobridges, Transition2Bio, Open DOORS (Interreg MED project), BIObec, MARINA H2020 Project, BLOWAYS, VIBES, BIO4AFRICA, MPowerBIO, AgroBridges, Glaukos, Tech4Biowaste, Allthings.bioPRO, Bioswitch, MUSIC, LIFT, RoadToBio, BioCannDo, InnProBio, Open-Bio, ReSolute, ReSolve, AgriMax, BioBased4SME, UrBioFuture, BEACON, BIOTOP, GRETE, DATEMATS, BIOEASTSUP, PAPILLONS, BIC - Biobased Industries Consortium, MycoKey, GLAMOUR H2020, AgroBioHeat, AlpLinkBioEco, Interreg MED Green Growth, FERTIMANURE, SEA2LAND, FISH4FISH, BIOSEA, Green Tech Lab, Transition to Green Economy, AlpLinkBio, REACT, FoodSafety4EU, ECBF, ICT-BIOCHAIN, POWER4BIO, BLUE BIO MED, eForFuel, ERANETMED, LIFE Force of the Future, BLAZE, Dendromass4EU, Tech4effect, Novagrimed, ENERMED, ELIHMED, GoGreen, Smart Ground , Remediate, Sugere, BlueCC, SECRETED, FORCE Cities cooperating for Circular Economy, BioplasticEurope, Susincer, Viroplan, SATURN, Remedia Life, FOODLEVERS, TECH4EFFECT, AFINET, VFA platform, EDCTP, MedEca, FIRST2RUN, NoAW, TERMINUS, ECIRCULAR, MADFORWATER, IEA Bioenergy, BPLAS, ENERMED, ELIHMED, BalticBiomass4Value, RehabLab, MERCES, BioSPRINT, Water JPI, Bythos, WeReLaNa, GoDanuBio, AgRefine, MD net (Interreg Med), UN SDS network, BIOECO-R.D.I., LESS WASTE II, European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, SIMBA, VALUEMAG; European Bioeconomy University (EBU), BLUEMED, WESTMED, EUSAIR, FIT4FOOD2030, NEWPACK PLASTICIRCLE, European Economic and Social Committee (NAT Section on Agriculture, Rural Development and the Environment), MicrobiomeSupport, SoIACE, MASTER, MICROMETABOLITE, BLOOM, MAGNETO; PROACTIVE; SAFENESS; SISAQOL-IMI, BioPhosphate, Nutriman, DAFIA, REFUCOAT, ENGICOIN, WAYSTUP, MyPack.</p>
<p>Impact</p>	<p>107 participants, 127 projects represented</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raised awareness on the EuBioNet among potential new partners • Animation of the EuBioNet community • Joint action plan (April 2021 to March 2022) of Awareness and Communication Activities, shared among EuBioNet projects
<p>Additional materials</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to the Agenda • Link to the full video recording of the event (EuBioNet at 1h.54m)

Table 8: Overview of the 22 April 2021 MML

As seen from the table above, the main objectives of the workshop were focused on co-creating suggestions and recommendations to improve the effectiveness and impact of the EuBioNet activities. To collect these inputs, the participants have been engaged in a participative exercise supported by three MIRO boards.

The **first part** of the discussion was framed around the definition of a common vision/mission for the EuBioNet 2.0: the European Bioeconomy Network of the future. How to improve the activities and platform to increase the EuBioNet impact?

The **second part** of the discussion was focused of **sharing the planned activities of the projects to design the joint time plan** and **collecting Actionable Knowledge** from projects to maximise their awareness, adoption and exploitation.

Beyond the live discussion, the MIRO boards have been made available to the participants and also to the registered people (that didn't actually participate), for one week after the workshop, to keep on contributing with additional ideas.

The report of the outcomes is structured along the workshops' objectives.

5.1 Attract additional projects and initiatives to the EuBioNet

The BIOVOICES final event was highly effective to reach additional projects and initiatives that never participated in EuBioNet activities before. Some participants already contacted EuBioNet to follow-up with exploratory meetings.

Another exploitable result is the database of participants, that were asked to provide additional information, like activities, interests and projects. According to the database, 127 projects registered to the event. Not all of them actually attended the interactive session, but the partners responsible for the EuBioNet are analyzing the relevance of the projects and initiatives, to start the recruitment campaign of new partners in May.

5.2 Define a common vision/mission for the EuBioNet 2.0: the European Bioeconomy Network of the future. How to improve the activities and platform to increase the EuBioNet impact?

This session was central to define how the EuBioNet should be improved to better respond to the members' vision and expectations. This activity had several objectives:

- Stimulate interest and curiosity of potential new members
- Promote the co-creation of a shared vision for the EuBioNet
- Improve, validate, and enrich the first ideas for improvement, developed by the EuBioNet.
- Collect additional ideas and suggestions
- Identify the most interesting improvements according to the members

The layout of the board supporting this activity was captured within a mind mapping board, providing the initial areas of improvement, and asking the partners to provide their suggestions by voice or using sticky notes:

- How could it be organised? very interesting but should be something different from the already running tools for partner search
- Collaboration among partners also depends on the needs of partners for an effective matchmaking. I need...I offer....
- (*out of scope*) Promote new partnerships for Horizon Europe calls

Activity 3: Expand the EuBioNet

Activity objectives/expectations

- Attract more projects (Interreg, EIT, Erasmus+, etc)
- Attract/Open up to more initiatives (BBI JU, BIC, AKIS, Bioeconomy Strategic Working Group (BSW), European Circular Bioeconomy Fund (ECBF), JRC KCB, Europabio, ICLEI Circular, Euroconsumers, CoP Education, Bioladies, etc.

Insights by the participants:

- Partners can be the best ambassadors. Fruitful collaborations could lead to a more attraction capacity.

Activity 4: Promote the EuBioNet

Activity objectives/expectations

- Success stories from the projects
- Video Interviews with EuBioNet partners
- Promote active engagement in the LinkedIn Group

Insights by the participants:

- Make a clearer visibility offer to host other projects outcomes

Activity 5: Stimulate the discussion

Activity objectives/expectations

- Thematic working groups
 - Awareness raising and Communication (AllthingsBIO.pro, Transition2BIO, BIOWAYS, BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT, BioCannDo, BIOSWITCH, etc...)
 - Education and Capacity Building (BIOVOICES, BLOOM, AllthingsBIO.pro, Transition2BIO, BIOBEC, UrBIOFUTURE, Biobridges, LIFT, BIOWAYS, BioCannDo, EBU, the Education CoP, BIOEAST (some hubs are focused in education) and the BIC working group in education, ect...)
 - Stakeholders mobilisation and networking
 - Mutual Learning and exchange of good practices
 - BIOVOICES, AllthingsBIO.pro, LIFT, Biobridges, ect...
 - Support the value chain creation

- Recommendations
- Position Papers and Policy Briefs

Insights by the participants:

- Good idea to organise working groups on specific themes. The group could try to sum up results from different projects; organisation of meetings
- Need sector groups to appeal to specific industries
- To "go local", it could be important to really understand the tools with which local governments could work
- Maybe instead of Support the value chain creation is more suitable "support to bioeconomy ecosystem creation"?

Activity 6: Events

- How the events functionality in the platform can be improved?
- Make the EuBioNet a single point to promote all bioeconomy related events

Activity 7: News

Insights by the participants:

- Collaborate with journalists
- Team up with network of communication agency or press agency
- Educate journalists and media

Activity 8: Directory of knowledge

Activity objectives/expectations

- (Connect/strengthen)
 - BIOVOICES/Transition2BIO Library
 - LIFT Library
 - AllthingsBIO.pro
 - @BIOVOICES social media channels

Insights by the participants:

- Provide a template where key results (reports, factsheets, etc.) can be uploaded
- Clear sign posting required to enable all to access the information - so more than a Directory of Knowledge
- create clusters of relevant H2020 projects outcomes
- If your audience include private sector, a directory may include business and investors profiles
- Avoid focus only on funded projects to avoid competition and hierarchy - with those shouting loudest getting the best attention
- Focus on Availability of validated bio-based products & services so we know what is available

and where and which are worthy of all citizen support

- Beyond of a repository of documents, the outcomes and particularly the contacts should be extracted from the 60 pages project report. People nowadays do not have time to read all the reports but to find valuable contacts or pieces of info
- Provide contents for Senior people. An example: <http://www.helpageing.eu/>

Activity 9: Valorise projects outcomes

Activity objectives/expectations

- Invite representatives to events (knowledge sharing)
- Facilitate the involvement of key partners in new projects
- Exploit results
 - Actionable Knowledge
 - Good practices
 - Data
 - Toolkits
 - Media
 - Make results more accessible

Insights by the participants:

- Create an advisory board
- Involve consumers orgs to have UX experience on board
- "Training" webinars for research partners on how to ensure impact of dissemination
- Guidelines/indications on how to exploit low TRL results

5.3 Share the planned activities of the projects to design the joint time plan

This activity was already experimented in November 2020, during the last Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activity.

The idea is to provide a **shared time plan** where the partners can share the activities that they are planning, to:

- facilitate the identification and connection with similar activities
- enable the overview of who is doing what in the next months
- avoid duplication of efforts (e.g. Organisation of a workshop in the same topic in the same period)
- maximise the impact and participants to events by joining efforts (e.g. co-organizing an event addressing similar topics from different perspectives)
- facilitate the match between needs and offer (e.g. I'm organizing a conference, I look for speakers, good practices)

Figure 11 Discussion board “EuBioNet shared timeplan for activities”

Barriers/hurdles

Although during the workshop, the participants were very active in adding their activities, several barriers/hurdles still don’t have a solution. The ideas shared in the first activity (see 4.2) only partially solve the questions:

- How to make this time plan alive, how to motivate the partners to keep on updating the time plan?
- How to support this exercise technically? Making it a live tool in the EuBioNet platform? Who can access? Only the partners?
- How to share a call for collaboration well in advance, to facilitate collaboration offers and ideas sharing, if the draft idea is not mature enough?
- How to group the activities thematically (e.g. compared to the November exercise, this board is designed to enable a first clustering of the activities)

This link (https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_LIOM6Y=/) provides the access to the EuBioNet shared time plan for activities.

5.4 Collect Actionable Knowledge from projects to maximise their awareness, adoption and exploitation.

The problem of lost knowledge is well recognized by the EC, the stakeholders and the projects. Each project delivers high quality contents that often remain underexploited and not available as Actionable Knowledge for the stakeholders or other projects.

LIFT BBI JU project was funded to provide an overview of CSAs ⁸ projects and to collect their results in the bioeconomy library. Transition2BIO will build on this work to create a library and toolkits in Bioeconomy awareness, communication and stakeholder engagement.

Nevertheless it is not easy to be aware of all the valuable exploitable assets and ready-to-use material generated by the projects, to collect, classify and make available them.

To support this process, the workshop made available a board to collect, per the 4 categories relevant for the EuBioNet, the assets available.

⁸ Coordination and Support Actions

Figure 12 Miro Board “available Exploitable Assets from the projects”

During the workshop (and after, since the board is available for the partners), the participants have been requested to add a picture and a sticky note with the project, the description of the asset and the link.

The picture facilitates the at-a-glance understanding of the asset and the link makes the access and usage very easy and straightforward.

This is a first attempt, generated satisfying results and can be used as basis for future improvements.

This link (https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_ILIOM6Y/) provides the access to the EuBioNet shared Exploitable Assets board.

6. EuBioNet 2.0 - A common vision/mission for the future European Bioeconomy Network

This chapter describes the EuBioNet 2.0, namely the **vision and activities** that will be undertaken to **increase the EuBioNet effectiveness and impact**, following the suggestions emerged during the last two Mobilisation and Mutual learning activities that involved the EuBioNet partners (in November 2020 and in April 2021).

All these activities will converge towards the definition of the Joint Annual Action Plan for Communication, Education and Stakeholder Engagement, *“to initiate or reinforce the existing synergies, and maximise the opportunities to, and the impact of, promoting the bioeconomy”⁹*. facilitating mutual learning, collaboration and impact of the projects and initiatives belonging to the EuBioNet.

6.1 Mobilisation and Mutual Learning

This activity will continue and will be reinforced, promoting Mobilisation and Mutual Learning annual events, the thematic working groups, the speeches at events organized by other partners and the capacity building activities. The EuBioNet will keep on facilitating and promoting these activities.

6.2 Better exploitation of the Actionable Knowledge produced by the projects

Projects are not aware of what other projects are doing and a large number of good knowledge is underexploited. Another issue to be solved is how to keep valorising the outcomes of the concluded projects. Often, after few years these outcomes are not available anymore (e.g. the websites are closed). This question is still under discussion, but an idea could be to link to the [Bioeconomy Library](#) developed by the LIFT project, where most of the results are accessible. Transition2BIO itself is developing a library, connected to the LIFT one, collecting the most relevant awareness, communication, and stakeholder engagement contents.

The EuBioNet will facilitate and support this activity, by linking and facilitating the access to online repository of results dealing with bioeconomy Awareness, Communication, Education and Stakeholder engagement. EuBioNet will also connect the projects with these repositories, to enable the smooth collection and valorisation of results in form of Actionable Knowledge for the stakeholders.

In addition, the thematic groups and the Mobilisation and Mutual learning activities are also expected to facilitate the knowledge and tools sharing.

Finally, capacity building activities on how to transform good outcomes into Actionable Knowledge for the stakeholders will be supported.

⁹ [A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe - Publications Office of the EU \(europa.eu\)](#)

6.3 Collaboration marketplace

Promoting the collaboration among EuBioNet partners is one of the most appreciated activities of the EuBioNet. Nevertheless, the willing to establish collaborations, especially when the projects or initiatives have their own agendas and task, is not easy. It is important to identify a need and an offer, implement tool and contexts to facilitate the matchmaking and make evident the mutual benefits.

Periodic Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activities are considered very useful not only to exchange experiences and lessons learnt, but also to discuss possible collaborations.

Tools like the networking board, where offer and demand can meet, could be effective. Nevertheless, those functionalities work better when the participants are together (even online). Open boards, or functionalities like the “call for collaboration” on the website are not very used (although potentially very powerful).

Partners search functionalities should not replicate similar initiatives (like Cordis).

From EuBioNet experience, the collaboration among projects and initiatives is particularly effective with regards to the co-organisation of events. The shared time plan of future events will be added on the EuBioNet website and will be a shared tool to understand at a glance, what the other partners are planning.

6.4 Thematic working groups

The EuBioNet could take a role in connecting and facilitating the collaboration, dialogue and debate among projects and initiatives focusing on similar topics.

The thematic groups could discuss shared challenges and co-create policy briefs, recommendations, or position papers to be delivered to the EC, policy makers, BBI JU (or the future CBE JU), BIC, industrial clusters, etc.

As mentioned above, four main thematic groups can be identified, clustering several projects and initiatives already members of the EuBioNet. These thematic groups are very well connected with the EC objectives with regards to the bioeconomy promotion:

- Awareness raising and Communication
- Education and Capacity Building
- Stakeholders mobilisation and networking
- Support the bioeconomy ecosystem creation

The first steps for the creation of the EuBioNet working groups are already planned:

- The **Awareness raising and Communication** working group will start with a meeting (already planned for the 11 of May) among AllthingsBIO.pro and Transition2BIO. Partners previously involved in BIOVOICES, BioCannDo, BLOOM, Biobridges, LIFT and BIOWAYS will be invited. The focus of this first meeting is to maximise the adoption and sharing of good practices and tools from previous projects.
- The **Education and Capacity Building** working group will be launched in the first week of May

inviting AllthingsBIO.pro, Transition2BIO, BIOVOICES, BLOOM, BIOBEC, UrBIOFUTURE, Biobridges, LIFT, BIOWAYS, BioCannDo, EBU, the Education CoP, BIOEAST (some hubs are focused on education) and the BIC working group in education, etc.) to a workshop to define shared objectives and set the basis for collaboration among parallel projects and initiatives.

- The **Stakeholders Mobilisation and Networking** working group will be transversal in most of the activities of the EuBioNet.
- Some discussions are taking place among Transition2BIO and the BIOEAST initiative with regards to the working group **Support the bioeconomy ecosystem creation**.

6.5 Improvements in the online platform

A mechanism to identify, at a glance, the ongoing and concluded projects should be made for the EuBioNet platform, as well as a categorization enabling the clustering of projects by main activities. The actual solution is not anymore suitable with the large number of projects.

Therefore, the new projects page (and also initiatives page) will include the possibility to select projects by type of activity/focus, ongoing/concluded, countries of impact, keywords, etc...

The collaborative tools, like the shared time plan and the collaboration marketplace will be redesigned to facilitate the exchange of information and to promote networking and collaborations.

With regards to the events, we would like to make the EuBioNet a single point to promote all bioeconomy related events.

7. Overview of the EuBioNet action Plan of Awareness and Communication Activities

Objectives	Activity	Action Plan
Promote collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> promote active engagement, open dialogue, interaction and collaboration among partners facilitate networking and collaboration between projects and stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Expand the EuBioNet involving new members Collaboration marketplace Thematic working groups <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness raising and Communication Education and Capacity Building Stakeholders Mobilisation and Networking Support the bioeconomy ecosystem creation Exchange of Invitation to conferences and events
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint timeplan for communication activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online shared time plan of future activities Calls for collaboration
Increase bioeconomy awareness and communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> support the transition towards a more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle. increase the awareness of environmental, societal and economic benefits of Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy raise awareness on the European Commission policies, funding and activities in the bioeconomy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thematic working groups policy briefs, recommendations, position papers News about the project's outcomes Better exploitation of the Actionable Knowledge produced by the projects Cross promotion of results Cross promotion of events organized by the projects
Creation of the innovation ecosystem for the bioeconomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> stimulate the debate, knowledge sharing and mutual learning to address bioeconomy related challenges and opportunity identify and diffuse impact-oriented strategies to boost the Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy in Europe 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-organisation of events Thematic working groups policy briefs, recommendations, position papers Participation as speakers to events (good practices sharing)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> promote stakeholders' engagement and networking activities at European, National and Regional level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cross-awareness of the activities organized by the projects and initiatives Co-organisation of events Participation as speakers to events (good practices sharing)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate the co-creation of actionable knowledge for the different stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better exploitation of the Actionable Knowledge produced by the projects Directory of knowledge Cross promotion of results
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> support the Member States and regions in developing awareness, communication and education activities on Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliver capacity building activities to member states and regions Participation as speakers to events (good practices sharing)

8. Conclusions

This deliverable represents the first idea for the EuBioNet action Plan of Awareness and Communication Activities, co-created with the EuBioNet projects through two (2) Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops (one promoted by BIOVOICES in 2020 and one promoted by Transition2BIO in 2021).

It will serve to guide the strategy to make the EuBioNet better responding to:

- the EC vision for the European Bioeconomy network as stated in the update of the European Bioeconomy Strategy 2018
- the partners' expectation, needs and ideas to enable the network to act more effective and impactful
- the need to increase the mutual learning, collaboration, exploitation of results and therefore impact of EU funded projects and initiatives

This strategic approach will also consolidate the EuBioNet robust position in stimulating the debate and delivering recommendations, position papers and policy briefs to increase its effectiveness in contributing to the transition towards the circular bioeconomy in Europe.

9. Annex 1: List of achievements of the EuBioNet

The following table lists the main activities facilitated through the European Bioeconomy Network from 2018 to 2021.

Year 2021	
	<p>8 March 2021 – Video Celebrating women who are promoting the bioeconomy</p> <p>EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Transition2BIO, BIOEASTsUP, POWER4BIO, Glaukos, MED Green Growth community</p> <p>Others organisations involved: Bioladies Network, BBI JU, European Research Council, Cnr, Minerva, Asebio, FVA new media research, University of Hohenheim, Plankton First S.A., Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS, BETA Tech. Center, Woolcool, Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra, Sustainable Innovations (SIE), Greek Bioeconomy Forum, University of Bari Aldo Moro, Bio-Integrated Design Lab, University College London, Novamont, Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant, Bioeconomy Cluster, Keracol Ltd, Ananas Anam, Embassy of the Netherlands, Brebey, ROELMI HPC, Università degli Studi di Roma Unitelma Sapienza, PEDAL Consulting</p>
	<p>30 March 2021 – The BIOVOICES Book for kids “What’s Bioeconomy?” – official launch event. The book, dedicated to children between 5 and 8 years old, was presented on March 30, 2021 (10.00 – 12.00) during an online event that obtained the patronage of the European Parliament.</p> <p>The book aims to explain the Bioeconomy and Bio-based products for daily use, while promoting sustainable lifestyles and consumption: in addition to children, the book is also aimed at their parents and teachers. Ad hoc training courses will be provided by the Transition2Bio project, supporting BIOVOICES in the dissemination of the book.</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Transition2BIO</p>

10 March 2021 – Faster project training activity to Tunisian researchers in agrifood (recorded)
EuBioNet members involved: FASTER, BIOVOICES, Transition2BIO

4 March 2021 – The Bioeconomy Innovation Week, a high-level virtual conference organised within the POWER4BIO project. EuBioNet representatives have been invited to deliver a Speech about Bioeconomy Awareness, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement.

More info [HERE](#)

EuBioNet members involved: Power4BIO, BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT, Transition2BIO, BIOWAYS

11 February 2021 – AlpBioEco final conference. EuBioNet representatives have been invited to deliver a Speech about Bioeconomy Awareness, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement.

More info [HERE](#)

EuBioNet members involved: AlLinkBioEco, BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT, Transition2BIO, BIOWAYS Allthings.bioPRO, GoDanuBio

Startupper School Academy 2021 – Special Bioeconomy Prize. This year BIOVOICES and TRANSITION2BIO together with the European Bioeconomy Network, Re Soil Foundation, Novamont and Cluster SPRING have decided to support the Startupper School Academy Program, offering the special “Bioeconomy” prize, which aims to raise awareness of students of a more sustainable economic model that uses renewable resources as an alternative to fossil ones. The activity includes training for teachers and high school students

More info [HERE](#)

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Transition2BIO

Year 2020	
	<p>16 November 2020 – Enabling Project Final Conference. EuBioNet representatives have been invited to deliver a Speech about Bioeconomy Awareness, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement.</p> <p>Organiser: Enabling</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Collaborations: BIOVOICES</p>
	<p>27 October 2020 – Bridge2Brands: FCA and Biobridges Call for Innovative Solutions</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organisers: Biobridges, BIOVOICES</p>
	<p>14 October 2020 – The wool value chain in Europe – Decision making process to support the creation of shared values and practices</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organisers: Biobridges, BIOVOICES</p>
	<p>24 June 2020 – Bridge2Brands: P&G and Biobridges Call for Innovative Solutions</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organisers: Biobridges, BIOVOICES</p>

<p>Advancing Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy in Central and Eastern European Countries</p> <p>Webinar 4: 15 June 10:00 CET Developing multi-stakeholder partnerships and co-creation for boosting the uptake of bioeconomy in CEE. Open to everybody.</p> <p>Organisers: BioEAST</p> <p>Collaborations: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT</p>	<p>15 June 2020 – BioEAST Webinar n°4: Developing multi-stakeholder partnerships and co-creation for boosting the uptake of bioeconomy</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organisers: BioEAST</p> <p>Collaborations: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT</p>
<p>STAR ProBio Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Bio-based Products Grant Agreement Number 727740</p> <p>Proposed techno-economic sustainability criteria for alternative end of life options and recirculation of post-consumer bio-based products</p> <p>Virtual Final STAR-ProBio Workshop, April 28th 2020</p> <p><i>Demetres Briassoulis – AUA-DNRAE</i></p> <p>Organisers: STAR-ProBio</p> <p>Collaborations: Biobridges, BIOVOICES</p>	<p>28 April 2020 – STAR-ProBio Final Virtual Workshop</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organisers: STAR-ProBio</p> <p>Collaborations: Biobridges, BIOVOICES</p>
<p>SHAPING THE INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM FOR THE BIOECONOMY</p> <p>Webinar 4/4 15 April 2020 11:00 CET Duration: 60 min</p> <p>VALUE CHAINS AND INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomass availability, quality, supply and sustainability • New value chains and business models • Open innovation platforms and facilities <p>Challenges, Gaps, Results and Recommendations</p> <p>Organisers: LIFT / CELEBIO/ BIOVOICES/ European Bioeconomy Network</p>	<p>15 April 2020 – LIFT series of Webinars – Shaping the innovation ecosystem for the Bioeconomy, to provide recommendations and Actionable Knowledge for quadruple helix stakeholders.</p> <p>Webinar 4: Value chains and innovation ecosystem</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organisers: LIFT / CELEBIO/ BIOVOICES/ European Bioeconomy Network</p>
<p>SHAPING THE INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM FOR THE BIOECONOMY</p> <p>Webinar 3/4 8 April 2020 11:00 CET Duration: 60 min</p> <p>FROM RESEARCH TO MARKET</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uptake of RTD results • Foresight, market studies and market roadmaps • Industrial roadmaps <p>Challenges, Gaps, Results and Recommendations</p> <p>Organizers: LIFT/ Biobridges</p>	<p>8 April 2020 – LIFT series of Webinars – Shaping the innovation ecosystem for the Bioeconomy, to provide recommendations and Actionable Knowledge for quadruple helix stakeholders.</p> <p>Webinar 3: From research to market</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organizers: LIFT/ Biobridges</p>

<p>SHAPING THE INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM FOR THE BIOECONOMY Webinar 2/4 POLICY FRAMEWORK 3 April 2020 11:00 CET Duration: 60 min</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardisation, LCA, labelling and regulatory hurdles Regional potential and bioeconomy strategies and action plans Stakeholders engagement and co-creation <p>Challenges, Gaps, Results and Recommendations</p> <p>LIFT, CELEBio, EUROPEAN COMMISSION</p>	<p>3 April 2020 – LIFT series of Webinars – Shaping the innovation ecosystem for the Bioeconomy, to provide recommendations and Actionable Knowledge for quadruple helix stakeholders.</p> <p>Webinar 2: Policy framework</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organizers: LIFT/CELEBIO</p>
<p>SHAPING THE INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM FOR THE BIOECONOMY Webinar 1/4 AWARENES Raising, COMMUNICATION, EDUCATION AND STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT 25 March 2020 11:00 CET Duration: 60 min</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness raising and Communication Bioeconomy Education Stakeholders engagement and co-creation <p>Challenges, Gaps, Results and Recommendations</p> <p>LIFT, URBIOfuture, EUROPEAN COMMISSION</p>	<p>25 March 2020 – LIFT series of Webinars – Shaping the innovation ecosystem for the Bioeconomy, to provide recommendations and Actionable Knowledge for quadruple helix stakeholders.</p> <p>Webinar 1: Awareness raising, Communication, Education and Stakeholders Engagement</p> <p>More info HERE</p> <p>Organizers: LIFT/UrBIOfuture</p>
Susanna Albertini (IT) European Bioeconomy Network EuBioNet 	<p>15 April 2020 – Virtual Techsummit – Covid 19 Threat or opportunity?</p> <p>Cooperation of countries and importance of cohesion during pandemic COVID-19 – Crisis management of country – Leadership</p> <p>Green a white page: the contibution of the EuBioNet and the CSA projects.</p>

30 January 2020 – REGIONAL MML: Increase Bioeconomy Acceptance involving Teachers and Students.

The main goal of the workshop was to raise awareness on bioeconomy and info-educate teachers and tutors as multipliers of knowledge, in order to contribute to the adoption of bio-based products. The meeting took place in the “Spazio Attivo of Roma Casilina”, in live connection with the other 5 “Spazi Attivi” of the Lazio Region, which are collaborative spaces where everyone, citizens, startups, businesses and local authorities, participate in the growth of the territory.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT

24 January 2020 – NATIONAL MML: Bioeconomy in Friuli Venezia Giulia. Focus on training and orientation to support sustainable and circular development

The Autonomous Region of Friuli Venezia Giulia and BIOVOICES project organized, in collaboration with Biobridges, AgrifoodFVG and the European Bioeconomy Network, a Mobilization and Mutual Learning (MML) Workshop.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, STAR-ProBio, UrBioFuture, Nextfood, LIFT

Year 2019

3 December 2019 – BBI JU Stakeholder Forum CSAs workshop

In the context of the BBI JU Stakeholder Forum 2019, LIFT project organized, in close collaboration with BBI JU, a Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop among the CSA projects, as well as selected non-CSA projects funded under different programmes, promoting the creation of an innovation ecosystem for the bioeconomy.

38 CSAs presented the lessons learnt from their projects and discussed the challenges still to be addressed for bioeconomy uptake in 4 facilitated sessions, involving more than 350 participants.

The workshop was supported by the European Bioeconomy Network, BIOVOICES and Biobridges projects

EuBioNet members involved: AlpBioEco, BE RURAL, BERST, BIO4ECO, BioBase4SME, Biobridges, BioCannDo, BioLinX, BIOMONITOR, BIOPEN, BioReg, BIOREGIO, BioStep, BIOVOICES, BIOWAYS, BISO, BLOOM, CommBeBiz, Enabling, Green Growth, Grenzeloos Biobased Onderwijs – GBO, ICT-BioChain, InnProBio, KETBIO, LIFT, Pilots4U, POWER4BIO, ProBIO, RoadToBio, RUBIZMO, STAR4BBI, STAR-ProBio, SUPERBIO, RDI2CLUB, Biobord

31 October 2019 – European MML: Shaping the bio-based economy involving citizens through a participatory approach

The workshop was promoted by the European Bioeconomy Network and was the satellite event of the “European Workshop on Bioeconomy”, hosted by the French Ministry of Agriculture and Food and organised by the BIOVOICES project.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, BIOWAYS, BLOOM, BIOSTEP

28 October 2019 – SCAR Bioeconomy Strategic Working Group (BSW)

The BSW discussed how renewable bio-resources can be sustainably produced for the Bioeconomy; Presentation of the European Bioeconomy Network and its role in raising awareness and communication activities to member states”.

18-20 October 2019 – BIOECONOMY Village at Maker Faire Rome 2019

The BIOECONOMY Village is an event format already successfully tested in the context of the Maker Faire Rome 2017, 2018 and 2019 fair.

Through the display of products, examples, thematic workshops and practical demonstrations, visitors are shown, in a clear and engaging way, how the bioeconomy is increasingly part of our daily life and how consumers’ conscious choices can have a positive impact on the environment, society and the economy.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, STAR Pro-Bio, LIFT

17 October 2019 – BIOVOICES national workshop at Forum Buy Green Compraverde: The bioeconomy in Italy: incentives, laws, norms

The day aimed to be a moment of sharing knowledge about the experiences, the regulations and the existing laws at national and European level, and the necessities to push the development of the bioeconomy at national level.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, STAR Pro-Bio

[More Info](#)

16 October 2019 – Committee of the Region Bioeconomy conference on Regions, Cities and Civil Society

Presentation of the European Bioeconomy Network. Speech on the importance of raising awareness at local and regional level: the role of the European Bioeconomy Network”.

15 October 2019 – Workshop on Bioeconomy Education organized by the DG R&I European Commission.

Presentation of the European Bioeconomy Network and its role on “Supporting Regions in the design of innovative bioeconomy educational paths: The contribution of the European Bioeconomy Network”.

4 October 2019 – Biobridges workshop at IFIB 2019 – New bioeconomy value chains from local resources: challenges and opportunities

In the context of IFIB 2019, **Biobridges** project organized a **co-creation workshop** to ease the dialogue among actors along the value chain (industry, policy makers, consumers, researchers, investors, feedstock providers, etc.) and to highlight challenges and opportunities for the valorisation of local resources in the bioeconomy framework.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOPEN, Biobarr, Power4Bio, Agrimax

27-28 September 2019 – The BIOECONOMY Village at the European Researchers' Night 2019

On 27 and 28 September 2019, the Italian edition in Frascati of the European Researchers' Night hosted the BIOECONOMY Village, promoted by the BIOVOICES, STAR-ProBio, Biobridges and LIFT projects funded by the European Commission.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT, BIOWAYS, STAR-ProBio

25-26 September 2019 – Science is Wonderful! 2019

Science is Wonderful! is a free exhibition which brings the world of science to the public. BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS and LIFT projects representatives shared, at their stands, presentations, activities and games.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT, BIOWAYS

[More Info](#)

26 September 2019 – Maker Faire Academy – The economy of the sea: valorisation of marine resources.

In the context of the Mini Maker Faire, BIOVOICES in collaboration with Biobridges and MISTRAL projects organized a regional MML workshop entitled “The economy of the sea: valorisation of marine resources. Balance between environmental protection and economic and social development needs.”

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges

[More Info](#)

8 July 2019 – The role of communication and education in promoting circular and sustainable bioeconomy at local, regional and national level

The workshop, a satellite event of the Bioeconomy Conference “European Bioeconomy Scene 2019”, was organized by the **European Bioeconomy Network** and the **BIOVOICES**, **BioCannDo**, **Biobridges** and **LIFT** projects, will bring together EU funded projects, European Platforms and Networks, Member states networks, together with quadruple helix stakeholders dealing with communication and awareness raising, to support the European Bioeconomy Strategy through communication activities.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT, BIOcannDo

[More Info](#)

24 May 2019 – INTERNATIONAL MML: The alliance between primary production and bio-based industries. A macro regional approach

The workshop aims to identify opportunities offered by the Bioeconomy, with a particular emphasis on its bio-based component, for the interregional development of Italy, Slovenia and Croatia.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, Power4Bio

[More Info](#)

20 May 2019 – **Startupper School Academy Awards** Ceremony

The H2020 projects **BIOVOICES**, **Biobridges**, **LIFT** and **European Bioeconomy Network** in collaboration with Novamont awarded the best Bioeconomy business idea from high school students. The prize aimed to sensitize students towards more sustainable economic model that uses renewable resources.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, LIFT

9 April 2019 – Bioeconomy as an opportunity to boost local development based on territorial resources

BIOVOICES project organises Mobilisation and Mutual Learning activities (MMLs), involving the stakeholder of the Quadruple Helix, to address the most relevant challenges to boost bioeconomy and the Bio-based market uptake.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOPEN

[More Info](#)

19 March 2019 – “Bioeconomy as an opportunity for regional development based on territorial resources in APULIA” was the first BIOVOICES Regional Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) Workshop in Italy.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, Power4Bio

[More info](#)

2019 – Startupper School Academy Program – Special Bioeconomy Prize

Also this year BIOVOICES project, Novamont and the European Bioeconomy Network have decided to support the Startupper School Academy Program, offering the special “Bioeconomy” prize, which aims to raise awareness of students for a more sustainable economic model that uses renewable resources as an alternative to the fossil ones.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges

Year 2018	
	<p>29 November 2018 – 10th Bioeconomy Stakeholders Panel</p> <p>The European Bioeconomy Network was invited at the 10th Bioeconomy Stakeholders Panel to discuss possible synergies and collaborations.</p> <p>EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS, BIOMONITOR, STAR4BBI, POWER4BIO, FIRST2RUN</p>
	<p>13-14 November 2018 – BIOVOICES Focus Group</p> <p>BIOVOICES involved 60 European experts to identify the most relevant challenges and key questions to be addressed to boost the Bioeconomy and the Bio-Based market uptake.</p> <p>EuBioNet members involved: AlpBioEco, AgriMax, Biobridges, BioCannDo, BioHorizon, BIOPEN, BIOREGIO, BioSTEP, BIOVOICES, BIOWAYS, BLOOM, CommBeBiz, InnProBio, ISABEL, RoadToBio, STAR-ProBio, Transition to Green Economy</p> <p>more info</p>
	<p>24 October 2018 – BioCannDo Networking Webinar on the Communication of Bio-Based Products</p> <p>BIOWAYS was invited to present the lesson learnt from the 2 years of project. The European Bioeconomy Network was invited to present its main achievements.</p> <p>EuBioNet members involved: BioCannDo, BIOWAYS</p> <p>more info</p>

22 October 2018, Brussel (BE) – Bioeconomy Corner during the high level conference: Sustainable and circular Bioeconomy, the European way
In the context of the High Level Event a bioeconomy corner was organized with the support of the European Bioeconomy Network.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS, STAR-ProBio, BioCannDo, RoadToBio, Agrimax, BioSTEP, CommBeBiz

Other EU funded projects hosted: FIRST2RUN, Leguval, Biobottle

[more info](#)

18 October 2018, Rome (IT) – BIOVOICES MML at Forum Compraverde Buy Green
BIOVOICES, in collaboration with STAR-ProBio organised the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop: The role of Green Public Procurement in boosting Bioeconomy and Bio-Based Products.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, STAR-ProBio

Other EU funded projects hosted: Urbanwins

12-14 October 2018, Milano (IT) – BIOECONOMY Village @Maker Faire Rome 2018

The BIOECONOMY VILLAGE at Maker Faire Rome, promoted by the European projects BIOVOICES, BIOWAYS, STAR-ProBio and Biobridges showcased Bio-based products to more than 50.000 visitors. Half pavillion was dedicated to bioeconomy, involving 50 national and European projects, research, start-ups, organizations and associations. During the exhibition BIOVOICES organized 3 MML workshop to discuss the main challenges related to awareness raising and changing purchase habits.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS, STAR-ProBio, BioCannDo, RoadToBio, Agrimax
Other EU funded projects hosted: FIRST2RUN, Leguval, Biobottle, ExCornSeeds

[more info](#)

28-30 September 2018, Milano (IT) – Bio Art Gallery at Altroconsumo Festival Futuro

BIOWAYS project, in collaboration with BIOVOICES and Biobridges, organised the first Art Gallery to showcase Bio-based applications in every day's life.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS

Other EU funded projects hosted: FIRST2RUN
[more info](#)

28 and 29 September 2018, Rome (IT) – BIOECONOMY Village at the European Researchers' Night 2018

The Researchers' Night hosted the BIOECONOMY Village, promoted by the BIOWAYS, BIOVOICES, STAR ProBio and BIOBRIDGES projects funded by the European Commission and BBI JU to promote Bioeconomy and BBPs to students and large public.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS, STAR-ProBio

Other EU funded projects hosted: FIRST2RUN

[more info](#)

27-28 September 2018, Torino (IT) – BIOVOICES interactive poster session – Side event of IFIB- International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy

Organised by BIOVOICES to validate the challenges identified as relevant for bioeconomy and Bio-Based products uptake, this interactive poster session involved IFIB participants and EU funded projects.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, BIOWAYS, Biobridges, STAR-ProBio, BioCannDo

[more info](#)

27 September 2018, Torino (IT) – BioCannDo workshop on bio-based food packaging materials – Side event of IFIB- International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy

BioCannDo hosted a product expert workshop on bio-based food packaging materials. In the workshop, the experts were asked to identify the issues producers and retailers face in relation to bio-based food packaging. Some EuBioNet partners have been invited as experts.

EuBioNet members involved: BioCannDo, BIOWAYS, BIOVOICES, STAR-ProBio

[more info](#)

27 September 2018, Torino (IT) – STAR-ProBio workshop on Bio-Based Products Social Sustainability – Side event of IFIB- International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy

The aim of the workshop was to validate and/or integrate a preliminary list of social and economic aspects to be included in a SLCA tailored to bio-based products. Some EuBioNet partners have been invited as experts.

EuBioNet members involved: STAR-ProBio, BioCannDo, BIOWAYS, BIOVOICES

27 September, Bratislava (SK) – Urban Summit in Bratislava

BIOVOICES organised the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop: “Strengthening circular economy in cities” during biggest “urban” festival in Bratislava, which focuses on various aspects of living in a city through discussions, workshops and presentations.

EuBioNet members involved: Transition to Green Economy, BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS

25-29 June 2018, Bratislava (SK) – Ecolnn Danube – Green Innovation and Entrepreneurship Summer School 2018
The event is part of the Ecolnn Project implemented within the Danube Transnational Programme and co-funded by European Union funds (ERDF and IPA contribution).

EuBioNet members involved: Transition to Green Economy, BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS

14 June, Nitra (SK) – General Assembly of the Slovak Bioeconomy Cluster
During the General Assembly, the projects have been presented to the participant stakeholders.

EuBioNet members involved: Transition to Green Economy, BIOVOICES, Biobridges, BIOWAYS

12 June 2018, Rome (IT) – ISAAC Final conference
In the context of the ISAAC final conference, the projects BIOWAYS, BIOVOICES and Biobridges, together with the European Bioeconomy Network have been presented to Italian stakeholders in bioeconomy.

EuBioNet members involved: ISAAC, BIOWAYS, BIOVOICES and Biobridges

[more info](#)

24 May 2018, Rome (IT) – BIOECONOMY Village during European Sustainable Development Week (ESDW) 2018 Showcase of Bio-based products to students and teachers. The exhibition was organised by BIOWAYS, BIOVOICES and STAR ProBio in the context of Sapienza University-Unitelma.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOWAYS, STAR-ProBio and BIOVOICES

Other EU funded projects hosted: Leguval, Biobottle, ExCornSeeds

[more info](#)

22 May, Brussels (BE) – BIOVOICES MML: Boosting circular bio-based economy in cities.

The workshop was organised by BIOVOICES, some EuBioNet partners participated as experts to bring to the discussion the project's perspective.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, BIOWAYS, Biobridges, ISABEL, BioCannDo, InnProBio, T2gE – Transition to Green Economy

[more info](#)

18 May, Bratislava (SK) – Green Day of the GLOBSEC 2018. The GLOBSEC 2018 Bratislava Forum took place in Bratislava on 17 – 19 May 2018. The “Green Day” part was held on the 18th of May in the morning under the heading of “Transition to Green Economy”.

EuBioNet members involved: Transition to Green Economy, BIOVOICES, BIOBRIDGES, BIOWAYS

14 May, Bratislava (SK) – Waking up Slovak Agriculture. Free Market Roadshow is an annual series of conferences, which visits around 40 European cities, featuring dozens of international speakers, which are accompanied by local speakers. During the Bratislava event, BIOVOICES project opened the panel and involved the invited EuBioNet members.

EuBioNet members involved: Transition to Green Economy, BIOVOICES, BIOBRIDGES, BIOWAYS

May 2018 – Launch of the European Bioeconomy Network. The European Bioeconomy Network was launched. The projects participating to the MML in March have been invited, a collaboration framework was agreed, the logo and the website, including some collaborative features have been designed by BIOVOICES.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, BIOWAYS, ISABEL, Biobridges, BioCannDo, ISAAC, T2gE – Transition to Green Economy, BioSTEP, CommBeBiz

28 March 2018, Brussels, BE – Mutual Learning Workshop organised by BIOVOICES in collaboration with the European Commission: Maximizing collaboration among EC funded projects communicating about Bioeconomy – Lesson learnt and recommendations. During this workshop the idea of launching the European Bioeconomy network was agreed. 27 projects participated.

EuBioNet members involved: BIOVOICES, BioLinX, ISAAC, BLOWAYS, SuperBIO, ISABEL, BioHorizon, RoadToBio, BioCannDo, STAR-ProBio, BLOOM, BIOBRIDGES, T2gE – Transition to Green Economy, BioSTEP, CommBeBiz, EMBRACED, InnProBio, STAR4BBI

2018 – Development of games to promote Bioeconomy BLOWAYS project developed four edutainment games in collaboration with STAR-ProBio and BioSTEP projects.

EuBioNet members involved: Bioways, STAR-ProBio and BioSTEP

Consortium

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